

MANUFACTURE OF CELLULOSE FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Highly aligned, discontinuous cellulose and cellulose/carbon fibre-reinforced composites have been produced using the High Performance Discontinuous Fibre (HiPerDiF) technology. With the addition of carbon fibre, the mechanical performance of cellulose fibre-reinforced composites changes from two-phase ductile to linear stiff. With constant fibre volume fraction (V_f), as the cellulose/carbon volume ratio decreases from 100:0 to 50:50, less composite defects appear. Correspondingly, their composite stiffness and strength increase (7 GPa, 146 MPa; 32 GPa, 412 MPa), while failure strain decrease (from 6.2% to 1.3%). To optimise the manufacturing route of cellulose fibre-reinforced composites, cellulose composites with three different fibre volume fractions have also been manufactured. The cellulose composites with an estimated $V_f \sim 71\%$ possess the best mechanical properties (8.54 GPa, 143.23 MPa, 3.03%) and the least composite defects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The demand for a significant reduction of CO₂ emissions is forcing the composite sector (*e.g.*, automotive and wind energy) to explore more sustainable and energy efficient manufacturing processes for lightweight composite materials. Large-scale utilization of natural polymers needs to be developed to reduce the dependency of the composite industry on non-renewable petroleum-based materials. Existing as the major constituent of natural fibres, cellulose is the most abundant natural polymer in the world with many advantages (*e.g.*, lightweight, nonabrasive, combustible, nontoxic, low cost, and biodegradable) [1]. The highly ordered structure of cellulose leads to its outstanding strength [2], making cellulose one of the best materials to produce sustainable reinforcing fibres for composites [3, 4].

As replacements of toxic and corrosive solvents, benign ionic liquids (ILs) are considered as a new class of solvents for cellulose, due to their chemical and thermal stabilities, reusability and dissolution performance [5]. Using a co-solvent with ILs has been found to improve the dissolution of cellulose by reducing the dissolution time and temperature [6] as well as the viscosity of cellulose solutions [7].

In our previous study [4], a one-step dissolution and cost-effective route has been developed using an IL/co-solvent for the dissolution of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), to produce high stiffness fibres with excellent specific Young's modulus ($\sim 28 \text{ GPa}\cdot\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) equal to E-glass. Highly aligned cellulose fibres have been dry-jet wet spun from liquid crystalline solutions (Fig. 1a), using high concentrations (up to 23.6 wt.%) of MCC (degree of polymerization ~ 200 -220) in a mixture of environmental benign ionic liquid (IL) 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium diethyl phosphate (EMImDEP) and a co-solvent dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The mechanical properties (Fig.1b), as well as the physical structure (Fig.1c-d) of these fibres, indicate their suitability as sustainable reinforcing fibres for industrial applications, *e.g.* automotive parts and sports equipment.

To further improve the mechanical properties of cellulose fibres, additives of cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) prepared by acid hydrolysis of cotton cellulose [8] have been studied as the reinforcing nano-fillers for cellulose fibres. CNCs produced are rod-type nanoparticles with surface charge (*ca.* 54 mmol/kg determined by conductometric titration for freeze dried CNCs).

For composite manufacture, HiPerDiF (High Performance Discontinuous Fibre) technology [9], invented and developed at the University of Bristol, has been used to produce composites reinforced with highly aligned cellulose and intermingled cellulose/carbon discontinuous 3mm fibres. This allowed the production of cellulose composites and cellulose/carbon hybrid composites with properties comparable to those of glass composites and glass/carbon fibre hybrid materials, but with a lower environmental impact. Commercial Cordenka Rayon cellulose fibres have been used for the initial manufacture of cellulose and cellulose/carbon composites, as well as the future comparison with our cellulose fibre composites.

Figure 1: a) Typical polarised optical micrographs of 23.6 wt.% MCC/1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium diethyl phosphate /dimethyl sulfoxide solutions at temperature= 25-105 °C; b) typical tensile stress-strain curves of 20.8 wt.% and 23.6 wt.% MCC fibres produced using different draw ratios (DR) (3.5, 4.0, 4.5 and 5.0); c) morphology of outer surfaces, cross-sections and cross-sections under higher Scanning Electron Microscope magnification of 23.6 wt.% MCC fibres (DR= 5.0); and d) Wide-Angle X-ray Diffraction patterns of 23.6 wt.% MCC fibres (DR= 5.0) [4].

This study aims to develop a feasible manufacturing route for cellulose fibre reinforced composites using HiPerDiF technology. Cordenka cellulose fibres, with and without intermingled high strength Toho Tenax carbon fibres, have been impregnated with thermoset matrix for the manufacture and property comparison of cellulose and cellulose/carbon composites with different fibre volume ratios (cellulose: carbon= 100:0, 75:25, 50:50). Moreover, to optimise the fibre/matrix interactions and composite manufacturing, cellulose composites with three different fibre volume fractions have also been manufactured. All the cellulose and cellulose/carbon composites have been tensile tested. Their cross-sections have been observed for the investigation of fibre/matrix interaction as well as the calculation of fibre volume fractions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Cordenka 700 Rayon cellulose fibres and high tensile strength carbon fibres (Toho Tenax- E HTS 5631) have been used as composite reinforcements, whose properties have been listed in Table 1. The fibres were coupled with a 43gsm areal weight K-51 resin film (SKChemicals), a bisphenol-based

toughened epoxy resin with a density of 1.21 g/cm^3 . PRIME™ 20 epoxy (Gurit) was used for mounting the composites for cross-section observation.

2.2 Composite specimen manufacturing

The HiPerDiF machine produces prepregs with dimensions of $5 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$. Four layers of prepreg tapes were laid-up in a semi-closed mould and cured in an autoclave using a previously reported method [10] to produce composites. All composite specimens were cured following the same procedure and curing cycle: the semi-closed mould was placed in a vacuum bag and cured in an autoclave for 135 min at a temperature of $135 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a pressure of 6 bar. After removing the specimens from the mould, burrs were gently removed from all edges using sandpaper. Glass fibre/epoxy end-tabs with a length of 50 mm were attached using epoxy adhesives (Aradite 2014) to all the specimens leaving a 50-mm-long gauge length.

Figure 2: Images showing FK, KFK, KKFKK prepreg tapes and composite specimen preparation.

Three unidirectional (UD) specimen formats were manufactured in this research as described below.

Cellulose composites and cellulose/carbon hybrid composites with the same fibre volume fraction. Fibre reinforcements with three cellulose/carbon volume ratios (50:50, 75:25, 100:0) have been made using HiPerDiF technology [9]. Four layers of the FK prepreg tape, depicted in Fig. 2, were laid-up in a semi-closed mould and cured to produce 50/50 Cellulose/Carbon, 75/25 Cellulose/Carbon and 100 Cellulose composites.

Cellulose composites with various fibre volume fraction. To optimise the fibre/matrix interaction, four layers of the FK, KFK and KKFKK prepreg tapes (Fig. 2) produced using only

cellulose fibres, were laid-up in a semi-closed mould and cured to produce 100 Cellulose (FK), 100 Cellulose (KFK), and 100 Cellulose (KKFKK) composites.

2.3 Tensile testing

Tensile testing of five single Cordenka cellulose and Toho Tenax carbon fibres were conducted on a Dia-stron LEX820 single fibre tester (Hampshire, UK), using a load cell with a capacity of 20 N and a resolution of 0.5 mN. Tensile samples were prepared with a gauge length of 2 cm.

Tensile testing of three-six composite specimens were conducted using an electro-mechanical testing machine (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) with a 10 kN load cell at a 1 mm/min crosshead displacement speed according to ASTM [11]. The strain was measured using a video extensometer (IMETRUM, Bristol, UK): black speckles were spray-painted over a white background allowing for a $42.5 \text{ mm} \pm 2.5 \text{ mm}$ gauge length.

2.4 Cross-section observation

After composite specimens were mounted in Prime 20 epoxy resin, cured, then polished perpendicular to their cross-sections. Their cross-section images were taken using Zeiss Axio Imager M2. The cross-section areas of fibres and composites were measured using ImageJ.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Tensile testing

The tensile testing results of all single fibres and composites are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 3. The stiffness of composites is identified as the gradient of the stress-strain curve between 0.1% and 0.3% strain according to ASTM [11]. Strength and failure strain are measured values by the machine during testing, displaying as a sudden drop in the stress-strain curve while being visible as a loss of any material connection between the top and bottom end-tabbed parts of the specimen.

Sample Name	Stiffness (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Failure strain (%)	V_f (%)
Cordenka 700 Cellulose Fibre	17.47 ± 0.49	489.33 ± 55.25	8.50 ± 0.96	
Toho Tenax-E HTS 5631 Carbon Fibres	235.68 ± 14.94	3411.20 ± 290.97	1.58 ± 0.13	
50/50 Cellulose/Carbon (FK)	31.55 ± 1.28	411.70 ± 12.86	1.33 ± 0.05	
75/25 Cellulose /Carbon (FK)	20.06 ± 0.71	298.40 ± 20.63	1.54 ± 0.07	
100 Cellulose (FK)	6.92 ± 0.26	145.87 ± 12.31	6.19 ± 1.27	62.7 ± 12.0
100 Cellulose (KFK)	8.54 ± 0.16	143.23 ± 11.66	3.03 ± 0.82	70.6 ± 4.2
100 Cellulose (KKFKK)	8.07 ± 0.14	144.07 ± 3.93	4.13 ± 0.17	66.5 ± 1.2

Table 1: Mechanical properties of single Cordenka Rayon cellulose fibre, single Toho TENAX virgin carbon fibre, as well as HiPerDiF cellulose composites and cellulose/carbon hybrid composites with estimated V_f .

As expected, as the cellulose/carbon fibre volume ratio increases from 50/50 to 100/0 (Table 1), both stiffness and strength of FK composites decreases while their failure strain increases. However, the stress-strain curves of both 50/50 and 75/25 Cellulose/Carbon hybrid composites perform as linear lines like single carbon fibres, while the one of cellulose composite performs as a ductile curve like single cellulose fibres.

For 100 Cellulose composites (FK, KFK, KKFKK), the strengths are all similar at around 144 MPa (Table 1). Interestingly, with more K51 resin added for the prepreg preparation (Fig. 1), the stiffness of KFK composite is higher than FK composite while the strain is lower (Fig. 3). This can be due to the better fibre/matrix bonding and higher V_f , which will be discussed in the following section. When the amount of K51 resin in prepreg further increases, the stiffness of KKFKK composite decreases a little compared to KFK composite, while the strain increases (Table 1 and Fig. 3). This means that the

amount of K51 resin is excess in the KKFKK composite thus starts to decrease its properties. Therefore, the KFK manufacturing route for 100 Cellulose prepreps and composites is optimal.

Figure 3: Typical tensile stress-strain curves of (a) FK composites with various volume ratios of cellulose/carbon fibres (50:50, 75:25, 100:0), and (b) cellulose composites with various V_f .

Figure 4: Optical microscopy images of the cross-sections of (a) 50/50 Cellulose/Carbon (FK) composites, (b) 75/25 Cellulose/Carbon (FK) composites, and (c) 100 Cellulose (FK) composites.

3.2 Cross-section observation

The microscopy images of the polished cross-sections of FK composites (cellulose/carbon= 50/50, 75/25, 100/0), and 100 Cellulose composites (FK, KFK, KKFKK) are as shown in Fig. 4-5.

For FK composites with constant V_f (Fig. 4), as the cellulose fibre ratio increases, the defects in composites increase and the fibre/matrix bonding seem to be worse, which may be one reason for the decrease of their mechanical properties.

For 100 Cellulose composites, the KFK composite seems to have the least defects that may contribute to its best mechanical properties (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Optical microscopy images of the cross-sections of (a) 100 Cellulose (FK) composites, (b) 100 Cellulose (KFK) composites, and (c) 100 Cellulose (KKFKK) composites.

The V_f values (Table 1) of all 100 Cellulose composites (FK, KFK, KKFKK) were estimated using Equation 1, by measuring the sum area of fibre cross-sections and the area of composite cross-sections on three random selected microscopy images (Figure 6). Interestingly, the 100 Cellulose KFK composite has the highest $V_f \sim 70.6\%$, which may be one reason of its best mechanical performance.

$$V_f = \text{Area (fibre)}/\text{Area (composites)} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6: Demonstration optical microscopy images of (a) 100 Cellulose (FK) composites, (b) 100 Cellulose (KFK) composites, and (c) 100 Cellulose (KKFKK) composites for the estimation of V_f .

4 CONCLUSIONS

Cellulose/carbon hybrid composites have the stiff performance with linear stress-strain curves, while cellulose composites have the ductile performance with a two-phase stress-strain curves. With a constant V_f , as the cellulose fibre ratio increases, the mechanical properties of cellulose/carbon composites decrease with increasing amounts of fibre/matrix defects. With the increasing amount of K51 resin for the prepreg and composite preparations, the mechanical properties of cellulose composites increase first then decrease; while the composite defects, as an opposite, decrease first then increase. The KFK prepreg and composite manufacturing route has been proved to be optimal for 100% cellulose composites with the highest V_f .

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